

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH OF THE POSSIBILITIES OF ENSURING DIMENSIONAL STABILITY DURING THE MANUFACTURE OF AN ARROW

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Abstract

Welded arrows are widely used as the main working element of earthmoving equipment. The wide use of such structures makes the task of ensuring their dimensional stability during manufacture urgent. After all, it is precisely the provision of dimensions within the limits of the designer's tolerance that contributes to the functionality of the product and the safety of its operation. It is shown that the optimization of the basing scheme in combination with the use of appropriate technological equipment provides acceptable indicators of dimensional stability.

Keywords: stability, basing, technological equipment, arrow, welding.

Arrows are a mandatory element of excavator equipment, lifting machines and mechanisms. The design of the arrow (Pic. 1) gives it the ability to rise

and fall relative to the digging surface, due to the lifting hydraulic mechanisms of the earthmoving equipment.

Pic. 1. General view of the structure - Arrow

Dimensional stability during the manufacture of the arrow can be ensured by optimizing the schemes of basing the product and using the appropriate assembly and welding equipment [1].

When manufacturing a welded arrow, it is necessary that the assembly and welding equipment provides fast location, reliable fixation of parts and the welded product as a whole with force clamps. Assembling of parts and assemblies without force fitting, which causes additional stresses in the metal, must be ensured, as well as unrestricted access to the places of installation (fixation) of arrow parts and assembly-welded assemblies [2]. The equipment must correspond to the developed technology, and ensure the sequence of assembly of parts and application of grips and welds, sufficient rigidity and strength to prevent deformation of parts of the welded structure, while maintaining their correct

position [3]. Very important are the necessary accuracy of the assembly of the assembly, the product within the specified dimensions and tolerances, which are given on the drawing, the welding of the structural elements of the arrow in the lower position (PA), as well as the free removal of the already finished welded product [4]. In addition, the equipment contributes to the effective removal of heat from places exposed to high temperatures during welding and minimizes welding deformation [5].

Basing is the determination of the position of parts in the product relative to each other or the product relative to the device.

A base is a group of points, surfaces, or axes that are used to base products or parts. The installation base can be any surface that contacts the installation surfaces

As a final stage, after positioning and pressing the parts of "Shelf No. 1-2" to the partially welded assembly, we fix the assembled parts with clamps (the sizes and frequency of clamps along the length of all available parts of the arrow are given in the technological map) followed by partial mechanized welding of the formed assemblies.

The arrow is almost ready, but the most time-consuming welding of long ta-rope seams remains, which should be welded automatically, so we unfasten the assembled arrow from the clamping elements and transport it to another two-post bender to complete (full) welding of the nodes in an automated way.

All actions for the installation of parts in the modular welding equipment are carried out by an overhead crane. After each assembly operation, a visual control of assembly quality is carried out.

The use of the proposed base scheme and assembly-welding equipment allows, in comparison with the basic technology, to significantly reduce the dispersion of the values of the installation dimensions of the arrow, which increases the functional indicators of the product, reduces the possibility of failures of loaded excavator nodes and reduces the corresponding risks.

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